

Peace and order: The inseparable partners to development

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Abstract

Development has several attributes. In the same way as there are a lot of factors that influence progress. These elements range from simple, technical, economic and social components. A common or not so popular yet very practical reasons why a country remain technically behind and economically stagnant is attributable to its internal peace and order condition. Discontentment, poverty, injustice, and lack of opportunities are some basic elements inimical to peace and order. It is believed that peace and order may be initially rooted from neglected basic social services, extreme poverty, and gross social inequity, among others. Dissecting the root cause of the trouble is a must thing to do by government leaders to truly address the issue. A place where peace and order are perverse is an area which is potentially or actually chaotic. Implementing plans and programs geared toward truly elevating the economic position of the poorest of the poor could be a good agenda. Transforming a place, region, or country from an impoverished to a better condition is extremely challenging. So, the aspect of sincere and effective leadership is highly needed in this instance. Development is very remote to be attained in the absence of sustained peace and order. In essence, peace and order are indeed a form of social development.

Keywords: Development; Economic Development; Peace and Order; Progress

1. Introduction

Peace and order are indispensable constituents in upholding political stability, social order, and economic development. It is said that when peace and order are present in our community there are many facets of human activities that are facilitated. These are but not limited to the growth of economy, increase of investments, spawning of job opportunities and enticement of more tourists. Economic development is the continued and collaborative drive among the policymakers, political leaders and societies that foster economic health and standard of living in a place or region.

Some scholars define peace as the absence of hostility. But, Dalai Lama [1] says that peace, in the sense of the absence of war is of little value to someone who is dying of hunger or cold. Peace can only last where human rights are respected, where people are fed, and where individuals and nations are free. From this it can be deduced that peace means the respect for human rights, well-being of people and freedom of individuals and nations. To Albert Einstein as cited by Sandy and Perkins [2], peace is not only the absence of war or hostilities. Rather, it means or includes the presence of justice, law, order or government in the society [3]. King, Jr., a famous human rights activist also viewed peace as one which must include justice in society. To him, true peace is not merely the absence of tension but the presence of justice [4].

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In this review, the author tries to relate the connection between national economic development to the peace and order situation of a country or region.

2. Methodology

This mini review made use of a combination of data mining and idea expository technique. Related materials used in the discussion were searched from various internet sites plus reliable reading materials.

Objectives

This paper aimed to meet the following expectations:

- Present various views or definitions of peace.
- Identify some issues that may compromise peace.
- List possible scenarios that may promote peace and development.

2.1. Peace Differentiated [5, 6]

- Internal peace or inner peace – is the peace of mind or soul, a state of calm, serenity and tranquility that arise due to having no sufferings or mental disturbances such as worry, anxiety, greed, desire, hatred, ill-will, delusion and/or other defilements. Internal peace represents the individual peace and normally regarded as true peace. UNESCO's statement [7] says, since wars begin in the minds of men, it is in the minds of men that the defenses of peace must be constructed. Internal peace is important because it is considered a true foundation of peace in society or peace in the world. Peace in the outer world can never be obtained until we make peace with ourselves [8].
- External peace – represents the peace in society. A peaceful society or good society has an important role in supporting an individual to get inner peace. Gandhi, a famous Indian leader said: Each one has to find his peace from within. And peace to be real must be unaffected by outside circumstances [9].
- Negative peace – a peace characterized by the absence of violence or war. This kind of peace could be considered the true or real peace because at the onset there is already the absence of violence or chaos. There is no effort done to make the communities and the surroundings peaceful. Negative peace is the kind of peace that exists in a country without putting much expense on the acquisition of ammunitions and armaments. Here, there is little budget allocated for the recruitment of soldiers to gain the artificial and usually ephemeral peace.
- Positive peace – a peace that involves preventing or ending direct violence. Unjust social structures and social norms are corrected to avert the occurrence of direct violence. Here there is an active effort done to curtail or end the trouble or botheration. There is a big expense for the hiring of armed forces and police personnel to maintain a tranquil environment and internal order. McLaughlin [10] says the traditional notion of peace which is the absence of conflict is not enough to bring about sustainable development. He believes that if a government ends armed hostilities by issuing a ceasefire but without addressing its underlying factors, conflict may resume, further disrupting business operations and exacerbating poverty, hunger and inequality. The eight pillars of positive peace [11] are:
 - Well-functioning government
 - Sound business environment
 - Equitable distribution of resources
 - Acceptance of the rights of others
 - Good relations with neighbours
 - Free flow of information
 - High levels of human capital
 - Low levels of corruption.

3. Multiplicity of Issues

There could be several causes or reasons why peace and order get rough in a certain country. Based on ADB report [12,13] one very important cause why peace and order has been seemingly not so fine in Third World Countries is due to poverty which might be the result of the following: a) very low or moderate economic growth, b) low employment opportunities and poor quality of jobs generated, c) failure to fully develop the agriculture sector, d) high inflation

during crisis periods, e) high levels of population growth, f) high and persistent levels of inequality on incomes and assets, g) recurrent shocks and exposure to risks such as economic crisis, conflicts, natural disasters, and h) “environmental poverty”.

Four factors influence economic development: human resources, physical capital, natural resources and technology. First-world countries focus on these four areas. While third-world countries, notwithstanding their good natural resources, will still lag behind if they fail to promote research in technology and upgrade the skills and education of their workers [14].

3.1. Impact of Human Resources

The education, training and skills of workers have a direct impact on the growth of an economy. A skilled, well-trained worker is more productive and will produce a high-quality output that adds efficiency to an economy. Lack of workers or labor can be an impediment to economic growth. An illiterate, unskilled, or underutilized workforce will be a drag on an economy and may possibly result to higher unemployment. Every citizen should be given a chance or encouraged to learn or develop a skill without cost. If majority of the people are skilled workers, then there will be no room for vagrants and idleness.

3.2. Investing on Physical Capital

Increased investments or improvements in physical capital like machineries, factories, hospitals, schools, research centers, and roadways, will cut the expense at the same time increase the efficiency of economic output. Modern equipment and factories are more productive than physical labor. Higher productivity leads to increased output. Workforce becomes more productive as the ratio of capital expenditures per worker increases. The enhancement in labor productivity accelerates the rate of economic growth.

3.3. Quantity of Natural Resources

The abundance of natural resources will affect the growth of a country's economy. The finding of additional natural resources like mineral deposits and oil, will give a stoke to the economy by boosting a nation's production potential. How well a country utilizes and exploit its natural resources has to do with the skills of the workforce, its available capital, and the type of technology. Knowledgeable and skilled workers are able to use these natural resources to stimulate economic growth. On the contrary, uncontrolled exploitation or use of these natural resources would be inimical to the people which may trigger social disorder.

3.4. Enhancing Technology

Advancing the technology have a great sway on economic growth. When the scientific sodality explores and creates many inventions, country leaders look for avenues to use these innovative technologies such as having more sophisticated manufacturing tools and equipment. The employment of advanced and much better technology means the same amount of work will produce more output and economic growth will be boosted at minimal expense. Scientific and technological creations plus levelled-up education for the workforce will increase economic fruit which steer a better living condition for all. Nations that acknowledge the significance of the above economic growth factors will likely have escalated growth rates and enhanced standards of living for their citizenry. A better living condition would bring about a happy and peaceful mental disposition of individuals, hence maintaining peace and order in the communities.

3.5. Prohibited drugs

The non-stop and seemingly unstoppable proliferation and distribution of illegal drugs brings disaster to any country. The presence of prohibited drugs transforms an originally peaceful place into a troublesome and problematic area. Sustained and massive campaign by the government to its citizenry against the use and effects of illegal drugs should be strongly done to curve down the unwanted effects of these social menace. In that way, there would be more time and resources for the country to focus on development efforts that would redound to the general welfare of the populace, instead of using their resources to run after the drug transgressors.

3.6. Imbalance distribution of wealth and opportunities

The big gap of wealth possessions among the citizens creates an abnormal social and financial environment which translates to hopelessness and discontentment. People with less in life usually encounter unequal footing with respect to availing of opportunities compared to those with more in life. Incidentally, these scenarios above-mentioned may spawn a feeling of perturbation. Such that the initially-trivial individual's emotion may later on influence his family, his

relatives and friends, and eventually to a larger group. The seemingly connected stance may transform into an unreasonable antipathy. This connected thought could be a threat to a peaceful and orderly society.

3.7. Unfair competition in many facets of human life

Life indeed is in a state of continuous competition, be it fair or unfair. Thus, competitions could be natural or artificial. What is wholesome and acceptable is natural competition. Sometimes, due to extreme unconscionable avarice, manipulative and immoral corrupt practices exist here and there. To the weak and helpless victims, this woebegone experience yields a negative thought upon those encounters. Unfortunately, these animosities may bring about displeasure and a long-term negative mind and behavior of the affected person. Remember external peace is an offshoot of internal peace. The extent and quality of peace in the community actually emanates from the state of serenity or mental disturbance of the members of society.

3.8. Eroding value system of society

Many believe that as our society gets more and more influenced or driven by technology, the good value system of the people or the community as a whole is gradually eroded. When the citizenry does not anymore practice good values, the chance of having a chaotic or disturbed society is very high. Proactive teaching and instilling of selected good values would be impactful to the value system formation or reformation of the people. If these things happen, then peace and order would be promoted and development is just an arm away.

4. Predicates of Peace and Development

4.1. Development in order to proceed must sustainingly foster the growth of the following

- **Economic:** Countries in order to grow need to uplift their economic condition. Everyone living in a country is practically affected by the production, distribution and use of resources ranging from basic goods and services, up to financing, technology generation, import and export, income and practically everything affected by the law of scarcity.
- **Cultural:** To succeed in any economic endeavour, the developmental programs and projects need to be carefully patterned or attuned to the culture of the populace. Culture may be defined as the ways of life including arts, beliefs and institutions of a population that are passed down from generation to generation [15]. Implementing an action plan no matter how good or unique it may be is prone to fail if the culture of the people is taken for granted.
- **Social:** Any economic development program needs to be anchored on social behaviour of the people. It would be very difficult if not impossible, to put into action or adoption something which the society does not dwell or adhere to. If ever a community will yield to that which it does not in fact believe holistically, such would just be momentary and is going to fail eventually. In other words, the programs and projects should be something embraced by the community.
- **Scientific:** In order to grow scientifically, a nation should keep exploring and advancing new knowledge methodically through observation and experiments. Science is an unending process of finding or looking for knowledge. In order to be equipped scientifically, a country should have a strong research base aimed at discovering something new and useful to man or society. For third-world countries, their limited capital should be used in pursuing a priority-based research agenda. The wise use of resources through genuine research is a real exponent of developmental change [16].
- **Technological:** Putting into use the outputs of scientific investigation is the reason why there is so-called technological advancement. Technology is the continuous process of implementing knowledge which may be either useful or harmful. Of course, a technology which is beneficial to society or to humanity is overwhelmingly preferred. Technology should be used to advance the lives and living of the people lest to jeopardize. More likely, nations that believe in technological innovations are those that occupy a better position in the global economic ranking. When economy improves, more opportunities are created such as high-paying jobs, better social services and improved environment for the people. A conducive surrounding breeds a community which is physically, mentally, emotionally and peacefully healthy.

5. Conclusion

After a thorough analyses of the issues identified above, the following conclusions are raised

- The big social gap between the rich and the poor is so inimical to the peace and order program effort of a country or region;
- Effectively implementing a sustainable socio-economic program may help improve the plight of the depressed hence promote true peace;
- Poverty could be considered a predicate of peace which in turn regarded as a predicate of development;
- An efficient communication system is undoubtedly useful in promoting and maintaining true peace and order; and
- A prompt, just and effective response mechanism for the disadvantaged sector may promote peace and order.

Recommendation

The recommendations below are offered for consideration, to wit:

- Implement plans designed at elevating the socio-economic, mental, and spiritual well-being of the citizenry;
- Reduce disparity of opportunities among the people especially the poor and the less-privileged groups;
- Create lasting programs to alleviate the poverty condition of the marginalized sector;
- Open an effective communication and feedback mechanism with the different groups in the community and the local government unit concerned.
- Design an equitable and highly responsive system that would promptly address the concerns of the underprivileged and vulnerable groups.

Compliance with ethical standards

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No conflict of interest of the author is found applicable in this article.

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Author's short Biography

Dr. Mario C. Nierras is a Professor at Biliran Province State University-Biliran Campus (BiPSU-BC), Philippines. A Monbusho scholar in 1997-1999 to Osaka, Japan on a Teacher Training Course in Mathematics Education. He has presented a number of papers in international fora/conferences in the Philippines, China, Indonesia, Sri Lanka and Thailand. He has published research articles in the Journal of Society and Technology (JST), Journal of Advanced Agricultural Technologies (JOAAT), Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (APJMR), Global Scientific Journal (GSJ), PEOPLE: International Journal of Social Sciences (IJSS), and Agricultural Research and Technology Open Access Journal (ARTOAJ), all peer-reviewed international journals. Dr. Nierras is a member of the following organizations: Global Association for Humanities and Social Science Research (GAHSSR), International Society for Southeast Asian Agricultural Sciences (ISSAAS), Philippine Association of Research Managers (PHILARM), International Association of Computer Science and Information Technology (IACSIT), Asia-Pacific Chemical, Biological & Environmental Engineering Society (APCBEEES), Philippine Historical Association (PHA), Philippine International Studies Organization (PHISO), Crop Science Society of the Philippines (CSSP), Philippine Sociological Society (PSS), and Philippine Association of Researchers & Statistical Software Users (PARSSU). Dr. Nierras is both a licensed agriculturist and a licensed teacher. He is also a Career Executive Service eligible. In November 2017, Dr. Nierras was certified as Organizational/Executive Coach Level One by the Institute of Executive Coaching and Leadership (IECL) based in Sydney, Australia. He presently chairs the Office of External Affairs in BiPSU-BC, Philippines.